

Morbus Bowen in the Os Pubis Region: Dermatosurgery as Treatment Choice

Jude Al-Kadiri

Onkoderma- Clinic for Dermatology, Venerology and Dermatologic surgery,
General Skobelev 26, 1606 Sofia, Bulgaria

Dr Adeeba Tofiq

Onkoderma- Clinic for Dermatology, Venerology and Dermatologic surgery,
General Skobelev 26, 1606 Sofia, Bulgaria

Dr Maria Malatesta

Onkoderma- Clinic for Dermatology, Venerology and Dermatologic surgery,
General Skobelev 26, 1606 Sofia, Bulgaria

Dr Estela Pabalan

Onkoderma- Clinic for Dermatology, Venerology and Dermatologic surgery,
General Skobelev 26, 1606 Sofia, Bulgaria

Dr Simona Kordeva

Department of Dermatology and Venereology, Medical Institute of Ministry of
Interior, General Skobelev 79, 1606, Sofia, Bulgaria

Assoc Prof Valentina Broshtilova

Department of Internal Diseases, Pharmacology and Clinical Pharmacology,
Pediatrics, Epidemiology, Infectious Diseases, and Skin Diseases. Faculty of
Medicine, Sofia University "St Kliment Ohridski", Sofia, Bulgaria

Konstantin Georgiev Tchernev Jr

Onkoderma - Clinic for Dermatology, Venereology and Dermatologic Surgery,
General Skobelev 26, 1606 Sofia, Bulgaria

Prof Dr Georgi Tchernev

Onkoderma - Clinic for Dermatology, Venereology and Dermatologic Surgery,
General Skobelev 26, 1606 Sofia, Bulgaria; Department of Dermatology and
Venereology, Medical Institute of Ministry of Interior, General Skobelev 79,
1606, Sofia, Bulgaria

Abstract

Morbus Bowen also known as squamous cell carcinoma in situ, is a disease which is characterised by abnormal squamous cells within the epidermis whilst the basement membrane stays intact. Higher prevalence is shown in older age groups and individuals with higher sun exposure. If left untreated the disease could progress into invasive squamous cell carcinoma, which could lead to local tissue destruction and perineural invasion. We report a case of a 53-year-old male presenting with a reddish plaque in the right inguinal area. Routine investigation determined the patient to have Bowen's disease. Dermatological management was deemed the best option with the benefits greatly outweighing the risks in comparison to other therapies. Surgical intervention proved to be successful showing no complications. This case highlights the efficacy of dermatological management for perigenital Bowen's disease and underscores the importance of early diagnosis and individualized treatment planning.

Introduction

Morbus Bowen, or Bowen's disease, first described by John T. Bowen, is a form of in situ squamous cell carcinoma of the skin characterized by abnormal

squamous cells within the epidermis without invasion through the basement membrane [1,2]. Thus, it is often called "squamous cell carcinoma in situ." [1]. Bowen's disease most commonly affects older adults, typically

More Information

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those over 60 years of age, and frequently involves sun-exposed areas such as the face, neck, scalp, and hands [2]. In genital / mucosal Bowen disease, human papillomavirus (HPV) - particularly HPV type 16 - may play a role in increasing the oncogenic risk [2]. If left untreated, some lesions may breach the basement membrane and become invasive squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) [1]. After undergoing surgical management this particular case of Bowen's disease was treated successfully.

Case Report

A 53-year-old male presented with a reddish plaque in the right inguinal area, which bleeds and grows over time, with a history of a year and a half (figure 1). Upon taking histology fine desquamation is observed on the erythematous plaque verified as Morbus Bowen. After undertaking diagnostic procedures (skin biopsy), the histopathological results indicated SCC in situ (Morbus Bowen) of the skin of the pubic area.

Figure 1: Preoperative view: A Scaly Erythematous Plaque with Crusting is Present on the Lower Abdomen. Appearance is Consistent with Bowen's Disease

Figure 2: Intraoperative View: The Lesion is Marked with Appropriate Surgical Margins. An Elliptical Excision is Planned

Due to Bowen's disease in the pubic area and an upcoming surgical intervention, a consultation with a cardiologist was conducted, as well as a consultation with anaesthesiologist to determine surgical risk.

On the third day of hospitalisation, a dermatosurgical approach was performed. The lesion was preoperatively marked (figure 2) and excised resulting in a circular primary defect (figure 3).

Figure 3: Intraoperative View: The Lesion has been Excised Down to the Subcutaneous Tissue. Clear Margins are Visible

The defect closure was done due to expandable plastic procedure (figure 4) and single interrupted sutures were made (figure 5).

Figure 4: The Intraoperative Stage Shows Active Surgical Excision of the Lesion. The Oval Shaped Wound Demonstrates a Wide Local Excision where the Surgeon has Removed an Area of Bowens Disease with a Safety Margin of Normal Tissue Around 4-6mm

The material was sent for histopathological verification, proved it was SCC in situ/ morbus Bowen, in the skin of the pubic area which was radically removed. The patient was discharged with improvement in dermatological status, in good general condition. Daily

dressing with povidone-iodine 10% ointment was recommended on an outpatient basis, as well as gradual removal of the sutures after the 12th-14th post operative day. No complications were observed after surgical intervention, highlighting a positive outcome of the dermatosurgical procedure.

Figure 5: Intraoperative View: Surgical Closure after Excision with Single Interrupted Non Absorbable Sutures

Discussion

Bowen's disease, also known as squamous cell carcinoma in situ, is a skin disorder characterised by abnormal squamous cells within the epidermis that haven't invaded through the basement membrane [1]. Clinical features of Bowen's disease include a slowly enlarging erythematous patch or plaque, which is well demarcated and has a scaling or crusted surface. In some cases, it can be pigmented or verrucous [3].

Bowen's often presents as asymptomatic; however symptoms can include itchiness, and bleeding, which can lead to ulceration and development of a formation which could be a sign for transformation into squamous cell carcinoma [4]. The main types of Bowen's disease are classical, subungual, genital, arsenical Bowen's and pigmented Bowen's disease [2].

Risk factors linked to Bowen's disease are excessive sun exposure [1]. Cumulative UV exposure induces DNA damage in epidermal cells and contributes to local immunosuppression, facilitating the clonal expansion of keratinocytes harboring p53 mutations [5,6]. Fair skinned individuals are also at risk for Bowen's disease as they possess diminished inherent defences against the destructive impacts of UV radiation [1].

HPV is a major risk factor for Bowenoid papulosis, a HPV driven with a histology similar to Bowen's disease [7]. HPV-16 is the most common type associated with Bowenoid papulosis and usually occurs in younger adults and often regresses spontaneously [7]. Men and women are equally at risk and the peak incidence is in sexually active people under 30 years of age [7].

Other risk factors (concerning Morbus Bowen) include, history of skin cancer, immunosuppression, chemical exposure especially arsenic, genetic predisposition, cigarette smoking, chronic skin irritation and male gender [2,8]. The risk factors ultimately lead to DNA damage. In the case of HPV, E6 and E7 viral oncoproteins lead to the inactivation of P53 and RB leading to loss of cell-cycle control [9]. A mutant pattern (diffusely positive or completely negative) of p53 was found in ~79% of Bowen disease cases [10]. Treatment of Bowen's disease involves a variety of strategies, chosen based on factors such as lesion size, location, number, patient health, and cosmetic outcome [3].

Conventional surgical excision with adequate margins remains a mainstay, particularly for well-defined, small lesions, often yielding high cure rates [11].

For lesions in cosmetically sensitive or functionally important areas, or where surgery is difficult, alternatives include curettage with electrodesiccation, cryotherapy, laser ablation, or Mohs micrographic surgery to maximize tissue preservation [11,12].

Non-surgical (topical) therapies also play a significant role: 5-fluorouracil cream and imiquimod cream - which can stimulate local cytotoxic and immune responses - and photodynamic therapy (using a photosensitizer plus light exposure) - which can offer a less invasive option with good cosmetic results [3,13].

Radiotherapy or radionuclide skin patches are additional options for patients who are poor surgical candidates or when lesions are in anatomically difficult sites [14].

Combination therapies or newer approaches (e.g. immunotherapy) have been explored in some reports; because no single treatment is ideal for all lesions, physicians tailor the approach to the specific circumstances, balancing efficacy, risk, safety, and cosmetic outcome [3].

Prevention methods of Bowen's disease include: avoiding direct sunlight and tanning beds, wearing sunscreen, and self-checks for any abnormal lesions on the skin [2].

In the case of perigenital Bowen's disease surgical excision is the preferred treatment, particularly when the lesion is well-defined, relatively small, single, or when there is concern about malignant transformation [15]. Histopathological confirmation (biopsy) is essential prior to surgery to rule out invasive disease [16].

There are three main types of surgical techniques - simple excision, Mohs Micrographic Surgery and Excision with reconstruction/grafting [12,17].

Simple excision involves excising the lesion with margins of normal skin [17]. For perianal or genital Bowen's, margins of 4-5 mm are commonly used for smaller, well-defined lesions; for larger lesions or those

in high-risk areas, wider margins (e.g. 6 mm or more) may be needed [18].

Advantages for using Mohs micrographic surgery are the maximal tissue preservation and evaluation of margins [12]. This is useful particularly in genital, perigenital, periungual, or other cosmetic/functional sensitive areas [19,20].

Excision with Reconstruction/Grafting is useful when the defect after excision is large or in a location where primary closure is difficult (e.g., scrotum, perineum) [21].

In some case reports, elliptic excision in the genital area followed by suturing has given good cosmetic and functional outcomes [16].

In a retrospective study of perianal Bowen's, wide excision had recurrence 23%, local excision higher, 50%+, depending on margins [18].

In genital Bowen's disease, simple excision has shown excellent clearance in some case reports, with good aesthetic results [16]. Wound healing in genital/perineal skin can be slower or complicated due to anatomy, moisture, tension, or movement [22]. Cosmetic and functional impairments (e.g. sexual function, urination, defecation) must be weighed when choosing how much tissue to remove and how to reconstruct [23]. Patient comorbidities, immunosuppression, and lesion size affect choice of technique [23].

Conclusion

In conclusion, Morbus Bowen represents an early form of squamous cell carcinoma confined to the epidermis, with a clear potential for progression to invasive malignancy if left untreated. Among available therapeutic options, surgical excision remains the definitive treatment, offering the highest rates of complete clearance and histopathological confirmation of margin status. In the present case, surgical intervention provided optimal disease control and favourable postoperative outcomes without complications, emphasizing the efficacy of precise excision and individualized surgical planning. Long-term follow-up is essential to monitor for recurrence and to identify any subsequent lesions, ensuring sustained remission and improved quality of life for affected patients. In the case of this patient surgical excision was chosen based on the fact that the benefits outweighed the risks. Follow up with the patient showed complete healing after surgery without any complications.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethics Approval

Ethics approval statement is not required.

Written informed consent for publication of their details was obtained from the patient.

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